

Effective Cash flow Management for Successful Project Delivery: Case Study of Selected Construction Firms in Enugu State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study dealt with one important, common but a rarely researched area in the project management value chain, especially in Nigeria; the effectiveness of cashflow management in relation to final project outcome was investigated. The study was set in Enugu state. It used data drawn from 6 construction companies, 1 consulting firm and 3 cognate public institutions to examine how cashflow management could influence final project outcome. A total of 92 copies of questionnaires were properly completed and returned. Analysis showed that cashflow forecasting returned a statistical value of 30.9 relative to the theoretical statistical table reading value of 7.4 while advance payment also returned an empirically statistically significant value of 12.6 against 7.4. Both values are significant at 5% critical level leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis and the conclusion that cashflow management in a project has significant implications for the quality of the final project outcome in both time and cost aspects. The study recommended that Job issuers should make reliable cashflow analysis and forecasting ahead of project commencement and that job issuers should make appropriate progress payments to facilitate timely and quality delivery

Keywords: Cash Flow Management, Construction Project Performance, Cash Flow Forecasting, Advance Payment, Project Cost and Time Efficiency, Construction Industry Nigeria, Financial Planning in Projects, Enugu State.

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Introduction

A project is a set of interrelated tasks executed in a given order of sequence to achieve a set objective (Godwin, 2016). In the engineering industry, most projects result in the construction of physical structures and their execution is usually calibrated along time lines. "Cash is king" in the construction industry, and that will remain the case, especially if we consider its constant need to finance large projects, withstand long collections cycles and manage cost overruns. In addition, construction also requires substantial investment to enable growth and modernization in an ever-competitive environment. Robust cash flow is required for the project to develop along its budget timelines. A project's cash flow is basically the difference between the transaction's income and its expense. The difference between a company's total income and its total expense over a period of time is the company cash flow (Anthony & Breitner, 2003). At the project level, a project's cash flow is the difference between the project's expense and the project's income. At the construction company level, the difference between company's total expense and its total income over a period of time is the company's cash flow

According to Fanning, Pendlebury and Grover (2003), forecasting cash flow of a given project is very necessary for a construction company to ensure that sufficient cash is available to meet their demands. It shows the contractor the maximum amount of cash required and when it will be required. It ensures that cash resources are fully utilized to the benefit of the owner and investors in the company. Fanning, Pendlebury and Grover (2003) pointed out three main ingredients that determine cash flow of a project to be: Expenses (cash out) which represents the aggregate of the payments which the contractor will make over a period of time for all resources used in the project such as labor, equipment, material, and subcontractors. Income (cash in) that represents the receipts a contractor will receive over a period of time for the work he/she has completed. Timing of payments: Cash flow analysis is also interested in the timing of payments related to the work done by the contractor.

Statement of the Problem

Cash flow is generally acknowledged as the single most pressing concern of the business enterprise (Rice, 2012). Walker (2011) posits that the effect of cash flow is real, immediate and, if mismanaged, totally unforgiving. He pointed out that Cash needs to be monitored, protected, controlled and put to work. According to him, there are four principles regarding cash management: First, cash is not given. It is not the passive, inevitable outcome of our business endeavors. It does not arrive in our bank account willingly. Rather it has to be tracked, chased and captured. You need to control the process and there is always scope for improvement. Secondly, cash management is very much an integral part of the business cycle. Thirdly, to effectively manage the cash flow, information is needed. For example, information is needed on: our customers' credit worthiness, our customers' current track record on payments, outstanding receipts, our suppliers' payment terms, short-term cash demands, short-term surpluses, investment options, current debt capacity and longer-term projections. Fourthly, there is need for the business owner to be a masterful Professional cash manager in business. However, unfortunately, this is not always the norm. In a poll conducted on the Better Practice Payment Group website during November 2003, nearly a quarter of the respondents declared that they never confirm their credit terms in writing with customers. You will find, therefore, that the cash management process has a double benefit: it can help you to avoid the debilitating downside of cash crises and, in addition, grant you a commercial edge in all your transactions. From the foregoing, it is obvious that without effective cash-flow management, it would be difficult for contractors and project owners to properly manage procurements, wages, and other miscellaneous financial disbursements incidental to project management which would predispose such projects to possible failures.

The study is delineated within Enugu. It will survey some construction firms within the state. Job issuers, consultants, contractors and members of staff of the ministry of works as well as those of the ministry of finance will be involved in the study sample since they all participate in determining construction project cash-flow.

Objectives

Based on the critical place of cash-flow management in successful project implementation, this study will pursue the following objectives:

- i. To assess the relationship between effective cash-flow forecasting and final project outcome.
- ii. To examine how advance payments influence timely Mile Stone Achievements for successful project outcomes.

Research Questions

- i. What is the relationship between effective cash-flow forecasting and final project outcome?
- ii. How does advance payment influence timely Mile Stone Achievements for successful project outcomes?

Hypotheses

This study will test the following hypotheses:

- i. Cash-flow forecasting has no significant relationship with final project outcome.
- ii. Advance payments have no significant influence on project Mile Stone Achievements.

Scope of the study

This study focuses on the role of cash-flow management on successful project outcome. The setting of the study is Enugu State. Thus the state's Ministry of Works, Ministry of Finance and Bureau of Public Procurements was surveyed. The study was not bounded in terms of time limits although the information generated mostly reflect current events and expectations in these organizations.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Literature

Cash Flow and Corporate Insolvency

In recent years, in Britain, about 250,000 new businesses are been created every year. Many destined to fail within the first two years. Argenti's research (2016) identified four main deficiencies that are the characteristic of failed companies, they include: cash flow forecasts, costing system, budgetary control, and asset valuation. Cash flow problems and shortage of working capital can, in extreme circumstances, push efficient and profitable firms into insolvency. It is also possible that a firm is pulled into insolvency by the failure of another firm. This "domino theory" may apply if a client becomes insolvent owing large sums of money to the contractor, or if a main contractor fails owing cash to one or more regular subcontractors. Arditi, Koksai and Kale (2016) explored the factors associated with company failures in the USA construction industry. They populated an environment/response matrix with Dun & Bradstreet's USA business failure data for the construction industry (fourth period from 1989 to 1993). Cash-flow management was found among the top factors behind failure of many companies.

Cash Flow and the Payment System

It is important to have a clear picture of a company's cash flow position at any point in the construction work. This is because it is easy to mistake financial ratios, as common not to have control over the cash flow in a company. Given the contribution to their working capital, the key issue for contractors is to hold the maximum amount of money for the maximum period of time. Contractors usually out-source labour, plant, equipment and services as a way to avoid the investment of capital in these areas. The main objective of a contractor is to recover a specific amount of money within a specific period (Tah, Thorpe & Mccaffery, 2014). They need return for the capital invested. Sub-contracting is often used as a technique to create longer payment periods. If the company has its own

workforce they need the money available to pay the workforce, for instance, weekly. In contrast, if the company makes use of sub-contractors, the money can be held for much longer, awaiting a monthly invoice and paying one or two months after receiving it. It should be remembered, however, that a contractor's pay-out is a sub-contractor's pay-in. When the aim is to win a contract, or to get more money for a project, overheads and risk margins are subject to manipulations. The estimating of indirect costs is a sensitive and confidential issue for construction companies. General overheads, risk margins and profits can be considered as indirect costs. There are not specific rules about how to calculate site overheads. The general overhead amount is generally determined by expressing the budgeted annual overheads as a percentage of budgeted turnovers and applied as a proportion of the cost of individual contracts (Barraza, Back & Mata, 2014). If the company is competing satisfactorily, the overheads percentage can be kept as it is. It may be reduced to win the contract, or may be increased if failure to win the contract will not affect the company (Tah, Thorpe & Mccaffer, 2014). Risks can be quantifiable and unquantifiable. For quantifiable risks, the appropriate costs are included. The costs depend on what is exposed to risk. For unquantifiable risks, the amount added is based on the management perception of the situation (Tah, Thorpe & Mccaffer, 2014). Sometimes, contractors overvalue the initial phases of their projects, so that they can have more money at the beginning of the project (referred to as "front-loading" the rates or bills). But to keep the overall value of the project unaltered, the final stages are undervalued. In order to get sufficient money to finish the contract, they have to get another contract. The cycle is repeated: overestimate the initial phases, to have more money, to use for completion of the former project. This might not be a serious problem in cases in which the company is operating and growing constantly. It may, however, be a serious problem if the company doesn't get another project soon. The payment systems, in this case would have to be very flexible. The UK's Housing Grants, Construction and Regeneration Act 1996 regulates the way that construction contract payments should be made. The existence of the law is, by itself, evidence that the practice of manipulating payments is widespread and unacceptable. The fact that the financial structures of construction companies are so dependent on the characteristic cash flow patterns indicates a need to understand better the relationship between financial structures and payment regimes.

Generally, the construction and engineering industry consists of a number of different units, each with its own unique operational and financial challenges. How these organizations interact in the project value chains is a key part of how cash is being trapped (Adel & Osamam, 2012). According to Akintoye (2010), there is a strong case for change in the industry that has the potential to deliver significant efficiency and cash-flow gains. However, it should be noted that change is not very easy in an industry with many entrenched practices.

Allsop, (2018) noted that the construction industry globally has long been characterized by long payment cycles, seasonality and lumpy cash flow, unpredictability of cash and, often, working capital gaps that need to be financed in both the short and long term. From the result of a study conducted by an American Express construction institute (EY, 2018), the challenges faced by the industry are reinforced by the outcome of the EY's study on the North American construction and engineering companies' financial performance over the last four years (that is 2014 - 2018). From their study using the most recent two years as basis for comparison, the analysis showed that in an environment of flat revenue growth, the company's net working capital requirement increased by 5% (with over \$2.1b more cash tied up). Simultaneously, debt increased by 11%, but cash from operations decreased by 6%. The situation was that more cash was being tied up at a time when finance costs are increasing and potentially reducing financial flexibility.

Cash Flow System Development Framework within Integrated Project Delivery (IPD) using Building Information Modeling (BIM) tools.

Integrated Project Delivery (IPD) helps to revamp project outcomes through a collaborative method of regulating project stakeholders' goals through creation of a platform that provide early participants involvement and shared risk and rewards. IPD does not include a tender stage to select the optimal bid, therefore, this paper presents a methodology framework to develop a cash flow approach using BIM tools. This paper adopts Activity Based Costing

(ABC), due to its ability to allocate different costs precisely to each construction process. Given that the BIM and IPD target is to achieve the best collaboration among project parties, the proposed framework backing this by displaying all estimated cost data of each package as minimum/maximum estimated cash inflow, during the buyout stage, for informed decision making.

Cui *et al.*, (2010) asserts that the mismanagement of cash flow in construction projects leads to several issues in implementing construction projects properly. The cash flow overdraft is caused due to the lack of cash flow management since the estimated expenses are less than the actual required (Kishore *et al.*, 2011). Elazouni (2009) states that the integration of cost and schedule is required to draw the cash out curve (S curve). However, the integration of cost/schedule is not effectively implemented (Lee *et al.*, 2011). The traditional integration of cost and schedule is time consuming and causes a significant waste of information (Kaka, 1996; Kim & Grobler, 2013). Kim and Grobler (2013) state that utilising Building Information Modelling (BIM) can improve the traditional cost/scheduling processes. In Lu, Won and Cheng (2016), it was shown that despite several studies analysing cash flow processes, most of research do not consider the differences between project delivery approaches. Since each delivery approach has distinguished relationship between project parties, therefore, the management of cash-out should be compatible with the delivery approach. Batselier and Vanhoucke (2017) exploited the EVM metrics along with the exponential smoothing forecasting model to articulate a systematic model of project costs and durations prediction inculcating cash-flow as an essential variable. In order to determine standard cash-flow management model for a project, Andalib, Hoseini and Gatmiri (2018) developed a model to predict the owner's financial behaviour during the project execution, using the previous financial records. Even though, the developed model gives a forecasting index with respect to the risk perception to similar projects, but generally were designed to predict the cash inflow, regardless of delivery approach used.

Furthermore, Carbonara and Pellegrino (2018) developed a methodology to determine the optimal values of the revenue floor, as well as, revenue ceiling. This methodology was designed particularly for Public-Private Partnership (PPP) and there are two caps either to share risks or revenue; these are the revenue floor to ensure the minimum revenue for contractor, and the revenue ceiling, which defines maximum profit can be achieved by the contractor, and any amount of revenue after the revenue ceiling will be shared. Even though this payment is partly similar to the IPD structure, however it is missing a crucial limb, which is the cost saving sharing. Moreover, the contractor in IPD could yield to zero revenue in case that the cost/schedule performance is poor. Lu, Won and Cheng (2016) developed a methodology framework to analyse cash flow, which consists of cash in and cash out. The developed model exploited the 5D BIM capabilities to determine the precise costs of resources for reliable cash outflow (Lu, Won and Cheng, 2016). The model used BIM tools for developing the cash flow curves, however, this study did not consider specific delivery approach for BIM projects. Ilozor and Kelly (2011) suggested that the integration of BIM and IPD can enhance the entire outcomes of design and construction process since this integration is associated with several parameters such as; cost/profit, schedule, safety, productivity and relationships. Lu, Won and Cheng (2016) developed a cash flow methodology that proposed detailed models for material, equipment and labour cash outflow using 5D BIM capabilities, however the delivery approach characteristics have not been considered (i.e. profit at risk sharing percentage for IPD approach). Extensive literature review is used to explore state of the art BIM tools and capabilities regarding schedule (4D BIM) and cost (5D BIM). Several methods reported in the literature for using BIM to develop reliable cash flows methodologies, and IPD's cost structure approach to successful BIM projects delivery. For the validation and applicability of the proposed framework, a real-life case study is conducted. Since IPD depends on sharing risk/rewards between project parties, this requires tailored cash flow curves for this kind of payment. The sharing risk/rewards system relies on agreed profit at risk percentages at buyout stage, thereby, the forecasted cash inflow will be proportional values, not exact numerical values as traditional delivery approaches. The proposed framework includes different scenarios for cash flow curves (cash inflow/cash outflow) to support decision making at buyout stage by exposing all possible cash flows to all parties before construction stage and accordingly maintain a trust worthy collaboration environment during the construction stage. Furthermore, this research addresses the inherent problem of schedule/cost integration due to the inconsistency between Cost Breakdown Structure (CBS) and Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) by exploiting the Activity Based

Costing (ABC) to estimate project costs, as well as the project schedule breakdown by following ABC hierarchy. Love *et al.*, (2011) reported that the cost structure, which comprises direct, indirect, and overhead costs, must be considered in the compensation structure approach, since the risk/rewards proportions rely on the degree of the achievement during the entire project stages. Therefore, ABC prevents this distortion by allocating the costs through multi-pools, and determines the overhead activities and costs needed to transform the resources into activities that can deliver the final product (Kim and Ballard, 2015). In order to address the issues outlined above, this research proposes the integration of cost and schedule into the optimised cost structure of IPD regarding direct, indirect and overhead costs, which is implemented through ABC.

Cash Flow and BIM

Interdependencies between the cost (BIM 5D) and schedule (BIM 4D) are obvious due to the integration between cost and schedule processes, in a single system, which is necessary to establish appropriate control. However, in practice, the two parameters are still separate, given that the schedule is represented by Work Breakdown Structure (WBS), whilst the costs are identified by Cost Breakdown Structure (CBS) (Fan *et al.*, 2015). Hence, during the budgeting stage, the integration between the WBS and CBS becomes complex, thus, leading to potential errors and mismatch (Jung and Woo, 2004). According to Fan *et al.*, (2015), the initial steps to integrate BIM 4D and 5D are creation of the project schedule and BIM models, and cost estimation of all design elements.

Subsequently, the generated cost items need to be linked with the project schedule (BIM 4D), and BIM element linked to the schedule. However, this process has some shortcomings when it comes to implementation, particularly linking the BIM schedule to the generated cost. Therefore, the BIM elements should be linked directly to the cost items to avoid the complicated process of integrating these elements with the schedule (Fan *et al.*, 2015). Kim (2009) developed a costing system model to manage cost estimation, budgeting and control, however, the proposed model (basic construction operation), which indicates the lowest level in construction operation that has linked to three sources, namely; WBS, CBS, and design files (Kim, 1989). This system has been criticised by Rasdorf and Abudayyeh (2017) due to it requires a high level of details, as well as, refining each operation in order to reach sub-task, which is not practical and applicable in AEC industry (Rasdorf & Abudayyeh, 2017). Since the classification of construction works is vital to reliable budget, Kang and Paulson (2008) developed a classification system based on four categories, namely; facilities, Spaces, elements and operations. Subsequently, the cost and schedule is considered for each level in each category for a construction project, however, the proposed classification system is not suitable for quantity take-off in cost estimation process (Wang *et al.*, 2016). Given this, the challenge of detailed cost estimation with consistent WBS hierarchy remains persist in AEC industry, particularly when using the work-packaging (WP) method, which relies on the cost/schedule control system criteria (C/SCSC) in the package level. However, this is not efficient, due to the construction operations involves long hierarchy levels to reach sub-task level (Moder, 1983). Even though the method assigns the cost to WBS regardless of CBS, nonetheless, Rasdorf and Abudayyeh (2017) assert that it needs some improvements to make it applicable in complex projects.

Cost structure of Integrated Project Delivery profile

According to Ashcraft (2009), the most important character of using the IPD approach is the compensation system to allocate the gain/pain ratios between project participants. The IPD approach needs a cooperative contracting relationship, which leads to motivate core team members to achieve project objectives. Therefore, multi-agreements should be agreed with all participants in order to determine the suitable compensation percentage to undertake the project. According to Thomsen *et al.*, (2009), the compensation approach structure must specify the methods which will be used to determine the proportions of Cost Overrun; Cost Underrun; and any other saving in the total budget under the agreed cost. Moreover, Love *et al.*, (2011) reported the cost structure (which comprises from direct, indirect, and overhead costs) must be considered in the compensation structure approach due to the risk/rewards proportions rely on the degree of the achievement during the entire project stages. According to El Asmar *et al.*, (2013), the IPD is more suitable with using BIM rather than project alliancing approach due to IPD procurement approach has the model which enables involvement of all project participants from the

conceptualisation stage and consider the compensation approach from this early stage, in accordance with the liable participants. According to Das and Teng (2011), the precise determination of risk perception is critical to ensure that the agreed compensation structure will be implemented properly through the entire project stages. Therefore, the risk/rewards ratios can be allocated fairly between the project participants, so that the participants who carry more uncertain works can compromise this with its profit at risk percentage. However, Delerue and Simon (2009) reported that the alliancing agreement can reduce the risk within sharing the information through the entire project stages, due to the succession in risk management process normally depends on the data availability, and subsequently, IPD enables this data through gathering all project participants from an early stage. Furthermore, Ross (2013) states that IPD three limbs can be concluded as Limb 1 which represents the reimbursement of project costs, in which the estimation of project costs must be scrutinised by using an open book pricing scheme. This limb must include all costs, which are expected to be incurred during the project implementation stages. Limb 2 which represents the overhead costs for all participants and the profit at risk percentage, whereas, Limb 3 is the profit at risk ratios, as well as, the cost saving. The literature review revealed that IPD integrated into BIM is the optimal approach to deliver construction projects due to IPD's abilities to maximise the value using risk/rewards sharing system. In the meanwhile, BIM tools can offer all the required technologies throughout the IPD stages. Moreover, previous research shows implementing BIM to articulate cash flow management is feasible, however, the 4D/5D integration requires a clear methodology to ensure all information will be exploited and presented in the project budget. Considering the IPD cost structure, previous research highlighted the shortcomings of existing cash flow system with regards to IPD, as the project parties need a cash flow system that shows the minimum/maximum cash inflow, and indicating all cost structure (direct, indirect and overhead costs) individually. Therefore, the ABC has been explored to measure its ability to optimise the cost structure, rather than the currently used RBC method, and the analysis refers to its validity to perform the IPD cost estimation process.

Cash flow and Payment options

i) Cash-in

Engineering project contracts typically provide that the owner shall make progress payments of the contract amount to the prime contractor as the work progresses.

Cash in = Cash receipt = income

Principal components of cash in: The principal components of cash include Value of work which is the actual work performed in the field. The total value of work done to date is obtained in different ways, depending on the type of contract and Material stored on the site, but not yet incorporated into work, as well as any prefabrication or pre assembly work that the contractor may have done at some location other than the job site. A step curve is used to represent contract cash income.

Payment Request for Unit Price Contracts

The quantities of work done on unit-price contracts are determined by actual field measurement of the bid items put into place. The total quantity accomplished to date on each bid item is multiplied by its corresponding contract unit price. All of the bid items are totaled and the value of materials stored on the site as well as any prefabrication or pre assembly work that the contractor may have done at some location other than the job site is then added. The prescribed retainage is subtracted from this total. The resulting figure represents the entire amount due the contractor for his work to date. The sum of all prior progress payments that have already been paid is then subtracted, this yielding the net amount of money payable to the contractor for his work that month.

Payment Request for Lump-Sum Contracts

Under lump sum contract the project is divided for payment purposes into relatively few work classifications, most of which are extensive and often extend over considerable portions of the construction period. Contracts progress

is customarily measured in terms of estimated percentages of completion of work classifications (major job components). The contractor estimates the percentage completed and in place. The total value of each work classification is multiplied by its percent completion. To the total of completed work is added the value of all materials stored on the site. From this total is subtracted the retainage. This gives the total amount of money due the contractor up to the date of the pay request. From this is subtracted the amount of progress payments already made. The resulting figure gives the net amount now payable to the contractor.

Payment Request for Negotiated Contracts

Negotiated contracts of the cost-plus variety usually provide for the contractor's submission of payment vouchers to the owner at specified intervals during the life of the contract. The contractor must make periodic accountings to the owner for the cost of the work, either to receive direct payment from the owner or to obtain further advances of funds. A common provision is weekly reimbursement of payrolls and monthly reimbursement of all other costs, including a proportion of the contractor's fee.

Retainage or Retention

A prescribed percentage of each progress payment is usually retained by the owner in accordance with the terms of the contract. The retainage may be held by the owner until the work receives final certification by the A/E, the owner accepts the project. Final payment is then made to the contractor, including the accumulated retainage

Final Payments

After the work has been finalized and all deficiencies remedied, the owner makes formal written acceptance of the project and the contractor presents his application for final payment. Under a lump-sum form of contract, the final payment is the final contract price less the total of all previous payment installments made. With a unit-price contract, the final total quantities of all payment items are measured and the exact final contract price is determined. Final payment is again equal to the contract price less the sum of all progress payments previously made. In all cases, final payment by the owner includes all retainage that has been held by him.

ii) Cash-outs

Engineering projects can make substantial demands on a contractor's cash reserve.

Cash out = payment of costs = expense

Principal components of cash out include "Up-front" costs (initial expenses or start-up costs) which are costs that are necessary to start the project such as costs of moving in workers and equipment to site; erecting field offices, storage sheds, fences; job layout; installation of temporary electrical, water, telephone, sanitary, and other services; bonds; permits and project insurance.

Payment of direct job costs: These include costs associated with payrolls, materials, equipment, and subcontractor payments. Payments for field overhead expense and tax. An S-curve (a smooth curve) is used to represent contract cash out.

The Contractor's Cash Flow

The contractor's expense on a project will typically exceed his monthly progress payment income over an appreciable part of the construction period. The cash shortage on the project must be made up from the contractor's working capital, or money must be borrowed to provide the necessary operating funds. "Cash flow" refers to a contractor's income and outgo of cash.

The net cash flow is the difference between cash out and income at any point in time. A negative net flow means expense are exceeding income, a normal situation on even a highly profitable project during the greater part of its duration. A determination of the future rates of cash outs and cash income together with their combined effect on the project cash balance is called a "cash flow forecast".

Factors that Minimize Contractor's Negative Cash Flow

Front end rate loading: earlier items in bill of quantities carry a higher markup than later items. i) This reduces negative cash flows in contract early stages. ii) Reduction of delays in receiving revenue. iii) Adjustment of work schedule to late start timing. iv) Coinciding the timing of delivery of large materials orders with the submittal of the contractor's monthly pay estimate. v) Delay in paying labor, plant hirers, materials suppliers, and subcontractors. This would reduce negative cash flows but undermine commercial confidence in the company. vi) Increasing the mark-up and reducing the retentions. vii) Increasing advance payment. viii) Achievement of maximum production in the field. i) Quick settlement or claims.

Major Cash Flow Management Techniques

Three core cash flow management techniques have been identified to help contractors improve cash flow management in construction. These are: Operational cost Estimating, S-curves, and Target Costing Techniques (Sanni & Durodola, 2012).

Operational Cost Estimating: Barnes, (2013) suggested the use of Activity-Based Costing for estimating the cost of resources as a form of operational cost estimating for construction projects. Kaplan and Cooper (2018) classified Activity-Based Costing (ABC) as a form of cost method which has recently been implemented in many industrial and service sectors to increase cash flow management in intricate production systems. It consists of a two-stage approach for allocating indirect costs to products based on cost drivers of various levels. In the first stage, resource costs such as labour, equipment and power are allocated to those activities performed in the organisation. During the second stage, activities costs are allocated to the cost objects based on selected cost drivers (example machine set-up, quality inspection and material handling activities), which express a causal relation between the activity demand and the cost object considered. Marchesan and Formoso (2016) noted that manufacturing costs to products and costs pertaining to product families, services and clients are all directly traced by contractors through ABC. Non-value adding activities can be identified through the information produced by ABC cost systems. For contractors to keep production in perspective during the estimating process operational cost estimating should be implemented. Thus, costs of non-value activities can be identified and estimated to some extent. Moreover, the changes that might occur after the initial cost estimate, due to the uncertainty of the construction environment may be taken into consideration.

Cash Flow S-curves: As described by Kim and Ballard (2011) the S-curve is seen as a simple technique used to present the projects cash-flow graphically. Used to estimate and control the use of resources throughout a project, S-curves are for simulating different scenarios, considering time and cost deviations, and for summarizing key information to be used when supporting decision making in different sectors of a company. Neale and Neale (2009) determined that due to its simplicity the S-curves may be implemented as a visual device for displaying information that is quickly understood in the working environment. This cash flow management technique is often used as both a cost and time control tool.

Target Costing: According to Maskell and Baggaley (2013) target costings' is used to reduce the total cost of the project in order to reach the estimated profitability while still guaranteeing acceptable quality levels. However, based on traditional cash flow estimating processes, cost is regarded as an input and not as an outcome of the design process. Cooper and Slagmulder (2017) distinguished that target costing is more focused on cost reduction during the design process which encourages cash flow managers to set target costs based on market-driven selling prices as target costing transmits the cost pressure placed on the firm by the marketplace to everyone involved in the

process of project design. Ferry and Brandon (2012) noted that most construction projects experience an overlap between the design and the production phases, hence the use of target costing in the production phase, by construction companies is encouraged.

Theoretical Review

The free cash flow theory

The free cash flow theory focuses on agency costs resulting from the separation of ownership and control. Managers have incentives to pursue activities that are not in the principal's interest, reducing the profitability of the firm. Furthermore, if manager's compensation is linked to the growth of the firm, they may have an incentive to pursue above optimum growth policies. They also may prefer growth, if pecuniary and non-pecuniary benefits they can consume increases with the size of the firm. Some papers analyzed the link between managerial compensation and the firm size (Jensen, 1976). Other research papers demonstrated that the elasticity between managerial compensation and the firm sales are twice as high as the elasticity toward the return on stock markets (Joskow, Rose & Shepard, 1993). Internal finances are preferred to external finances by managers as they can more easily evade market scrutiny. Jensen theorizes that managers can limit the agency problems of free cash flow by issuing debt and paying the proceeds back to shareholders. This course of action will reduce the free cash flow available to the managers' discretion. If investors (shareholders) are acting rationally, they will diversify their portfolio by exchanging shares for bonds, resulting in a constant return on their investment portfolio. Leverage restricts the use of the internal finance generated by the firm, forcing the managers to use cash flow to meet their contractually specified interest obligations. Furthermore, managers' incentives to invest in negative NPV projects are reduced, as firms have a higher probability of going bankrupt (Jensen, 1983). The free cash flow theory has very important implications for the effect of leverage on investment/financing decisions. The free cash flow model implies that for an over-investor, an increase in leverage should lead to a reduction in unprofitable investment spending. Additional leverage does not significantly affect the overall level of internal funds, but rather tightens the control and improves the efficiency of investments. If leverage (debt) pushes out negative NPV projects, overall investment returns will improve, increasing the firm's stock price. Indeed, most cited empirical studies show evidence of a positive relationship between share prices and leverage increasing transactions. The free cash flow theory presents debt primarily as a measure of control, and not as a source of funds, as debt acts to restrict managers' ability to pursue unprofitable projects that do not increase investor wealth. When a firm that was previously over-investing in negative NPV projects increases its leverage, investment expenditures should decline as this policy reflects the firm's commitment to pledge free cash flow to investors. Blair and Litan (Jensen, 1987) use a similar argument to suggest that their findings are consistent with the predictions of the free cash flow theory.

Empirical Review

Cash-flow Forecasting and Quality Project Outcome

Optimal performance in the construction industry requires maintaining an optimum cash fund. This, in turn calls for proper management of cash flows (Matoha, 2007). Firms with good cash management systems are able to make the necessary investment decisions to compete in the industry (Matoha, 2007). In a study by Shaban (2008) on factors affecting performance of construction projects in Gaza, Palestine, he found that the main issues affecting performance were cash flow management, cost, time management and safety. A study by Mutti and Hughes (2012) on cash flow management of construction firms in the UK revealed that insolvencies are higher in the construction industry as compared to other sectors, citing the major cause of failure as lack of financial control and poor cash flow management. The study elaborates that with good cash flow management, such companies can be kept operational and financially healthy. Failure can be prevented using models of cash flow management and forecasting that form a basis for managers to rethink their cash flow management practices. Nguku (2015) studied the survival of construction companies in Kenya and found that a combination of many factors have made the construction industry very volatile, less profitable and more competitive making survival of firms in the industry very challenging.

Intense competition and increased volatility have made the industry more vulnerable to fluctuations in demand and survival has been an uphill task. This thus calls for better strategies to ensure they are able to navigate and adapt to the continuous dynamic market turbulences (Baum and Wally, 2013). The relationship between cash flows management and market performance was a subject of contradictory views in the past. Jabbari *et al.*, (2013) on a study that examined the role of operational cash flow and its ability to predict a stock price crash found that the more the amount of operating cash flow, the less the risk of stock price crash. This, in other words, is in favour of a good cash flow management system being used to predict the stock market performance of a security asset. In contrast, Cheng *et al.*, (2008) did a study to investigate if cash flows are relevant for stock pricing in Malaysia, his findings were that though cash flows appear to have no information content on share prices in the annual and medium windows tests, it does have information in the short window tests with incremental information content beyond earnings. However we cannot generalize these findings in our domestic scenario due to some country specific differences, such as levels of development, competition, government regulation, etc.

Advance payments and Timely Milestone achievements in a Project

Ahadzie, Proverbs & Olomolaiye (2017) investigated the critical success criteria for successful building projects in Ghana and found that timely advancement of funds for project tranches due for implementation was crucial in the final success of the most of the projects surveyed. Timely advance payments for project scope management also featured as a key factor in the research conducted by Odusami (2013) on Nigerian construction projects. The study tested the effect of timely disbursement of funds to the project contractor on overall project quality and found that team leader's supervisory skills, professionalism, leadership style and project team composition was significantly augmented by timely resource disbursements.

Auma (2014) did a similar study in Kenya and found an increase in the number of stalled projects due to problems of cash flow and liquidity, time management and the leadership style adopted on site. Her remarks on the industry revealed that part of the reasons for failure in the industry in the complex nature of it with a large number of parties involved such as clients, contractors, consultants, stakeholders, investors, regulators and others. While it is very important to have a good knowledge of Project Management for jobs to be successful, proper management of cash flow and liquidity plays a central role in the entire activity chain (Nguku, 2015). The study concluded that funding need analysis should be conducted by every contractor and this should be clearly communicated to clients for successful project implementation process

Summary of Empirical Review

The subject of cash flow has received a lot of attention from business managers and is among the areas that will continue to attract research efforts from scholars given its strategic place in the successful operation of firms and contractors. Among contractors, cash flow issues form very sensitive layer of the business concern because it is a major determinant of success or failure in projects. From the works reviewed, Matoha, (2007) argues that with sufficient cash flow, contractors are able to make the necessary investment decisions to survive while Auma (2014) holds that poor cash-flow is responsible for most stalled projects. This points to the importance of cash flow in project implementation. It has also been argued that owing to the nature of cash flow in the construction industry, the industry records more bankruptcies than other industries on the average, (Mutti & Hughes, 2012). These studies and several others seem to establish a strong connection with the idea that cash flow remains centrally important for a successful project outcome. Thus, it becomes pertinent to question why the real life practice appears to negate this reality as job owners still find it had to maintain regular payments to help the project progress along the budgeted time and cost schedules. Most abandoned projects in Nigeria, for instance, have some link with irregular cash flow with the consequent attraction to both term loans and overdrafts to cover the cash flow gap. These end up forcing the job into the region of time and cost overrun and in, extreme cases, into abandonment. This study intends to examine how cash flow forecasting, advance payments and progress payments can influence the cash flow of a job and determine the quality of project outcome in the end.

Gap in Empirical Literature

While the subject of supervision in project management has attracted wide interests in research, one fact that has pervaded these studies has been the lack of multidisciplinary approach in the investigation approach. Most of the previous works have done indepth analysis of supervision factors but limited their enquiry to core building engineering fields. This has produced outcomes that reflected built-in bias. In this study, the multidisciplinary approach was adopted in the primary survey. Respondents from all works related to the final project production were included in the survey; ministry of finance, works, public procurement, consultants, architects, estate managers, surveyors and building engineers as well as clients. This approach ensured that balanced and unbiased responses were drawn from the sample and the outcome is reliable for policy purposes.

Methodology

Research Design

The study is delineated in Enugu. It will survey some construction firms in Enugu metropolis. Job issuers, consultants, contractors and members of staff of the ministry of works as well as those of the ministry of finance and bureau of public procurements will be involved in the study sample of respondents since all these actively participate in determining the nature and extent of cash flow in construction projects as well as in project cash flow management. The study will adopt the Chi Square statistical method to analyze the outcome of the questionnaire and use a combination of simple random sampling technique and purposive sampling methods to select its sample.

Sources of Data

The sources of data for this study consist of the responses from the sample population as highlighted in the research design above which formed the basis of the analysis and findings of the research.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of senior staff members of the Enugu State Ministry of works, state Federal Bureau of Procurements, State Ministry of Finance and senior employees of five construction companies in Enugu as well as their Consultants. However, for the unique purposes of this study, the final sample shall be selected on the bases the purposive criterion: we shall include all employees in strategic positions relative to the subject of our study. Thus all Heads of core functional units, field officers, project supervisors shall be selected into the final sample while all the key members of the contracting firms as well as the consulting firms shall be included in the final sample. Following this, the population of study is as presented in table 1 below.

Table 1. Population of the Study

S/N	Organization	Heads of strategic Units	Other Employee	Senior	Total
1	State Ministry of Finance	8	38		46
2	Ministry of Works	6	30		36
3	Bureau of public procurements	4	20		24
4	Akiota Works Ltd*	12	54		66
5	Con Engineering Ltd*	3	30		33
6	Chris Ejik Int'l Agencies Ltd*	4	28		32
7	Njonas Engineering Nig Ltd*	5	33		38
8	Metrohamon Engineering Ltd*	3	34		37
9	Veetek Nigeria Ltd**	2	12		14
10	Diyokes Consultants Ltd**	2	26		28
	Total	49	305		354

(* Refers to the contracting Engineering Firms, ** Refers to the consultants)

Source: Researchers computations from field study, 2025.

From Table 1 above, we have 49 unit heads, 305 senior staffers making a total of 354 individuals in our population frame. All the 49 heads of units will be automatically included in the sample since they are the ones who take major

decisions on the issues concerning payments to contractors and management of those payments which determine the cash flow. However, simple random sampling will be implemented upon the senior staffers to determine who will be included.

Determination of Sample size

As highlighted above, 49 individuals who are heads of strategic units in these companies are automatic candidates in the sample. To select the remaining portion of the sample from the 305 senior staff members, the study adopted the simple “Draw without Replacement” method. Thus, for each organization, we write “Yes” and “No” in small folded papers in equal amounts. The sum of these must equal the number of senior staffers constituting the population from where I will sample for this particular organization. In this way, the selection of people into the sample was randomized.

Table 2. Determination of Sample Size.

S/N	Organization	Heads of strategic Units	Other Senior Employee	Total
1	State Ministry of Finance	8	18	26
2	Ministry of Works	6	15	21
3	Bureau of public procurements	4	10	14
4	Akiota Works Ltd*	12	27	39
5	Con Engineering Ltd*	3	15	18
6	Chris Ejik Int’l Agencies Ltd*	4	14	18
7	Njonas Engineering Nig Ltd*	5	17	22
8	Metrohamon Engineering Ltd*	3	17	20
9	Veetek Nigeria Ltd**	2	6	8
10	Diyokes Consultants Ltd**	2	13	15
	Total	49	152	201

Source: Researchers computations from field study, 2025.

Instrument of the Study and Validation.

The instrument of study is a simple structured questionnaire, which is organized in a manner that addresses the key issues in the study objectives and research questions. The document is comprehensive and is made easy to understand by the respondents. The method of questioning used is the semantic differential type such as: Totally Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree and Totally Disagree.

The instrument is validated at two stages; first, the document is subjected to a small group of respondents called (pilot group) for completion. The responses of this group indicated that some propositions were not clear. Such propositions were dropped from the final document. Second, the instrument is submitted to the research supervisor for vetting. This stage also caused more questions to be dropped from the draft. The final proposition was considered good for the respondents and also good to capture the purpose and objectives of the study.

Administration of Questionnaire

The researcher shall employ the assistance of about 6 youth corps members for ease and quick conclusion of the process. The corpse members will be well orientated and instructed on the administration modalities before they are to embark on the task. This strategy is in order to ensure the work is done within the time frame allocated to the exercise. The administration is expected to last three weeks. Reminders, calls, discussions, verbal encouragements will all be employed to motivate quick and proper responses from the volunteers.

Reliability of the Instrument

The study adopted the Crumbach Alpha approach to test the reliability of the study instrument. This approach yielded an index of 0.78 which implies that the instrument was reliable to the tune of 78%.

Method of Data Analysis

Two methods of analysis shall be adopted for the data analysis. One method will consist in the use of simple descriptive analytical tools. The second method shall be the test of hypothesis using X^2 (chi-square) non-parametric statistical tool given by the statistic:

$$X^2 = \frac{\sum fo - \sum fe}{\sum fe}$$

Where

fo = observed frequency

fe = expected frequency

Decision Rule: = If X^2 calculated is $\geq X^2$ table reading, then reject H_0 and Accept H_A .

Data Presentation and Analysis

Analysis of Questionnaire Return Rate

This section shows the rate of questionnaire return by the case study organizations sampled. Table 4:1 demonstrates this.

Table 3. Analysis of Questionnaire Return Rate

S/N	Organization	Questionnaires distributed	Questionnaires Returned	% returned
1	State Ministry of Finance	26	12	46
2	Ministry of Works	21	10	48
3	Bureau of public procurements	14	8	57
4	Akiota Works Ltd*	39	12	31
5	Con Engineering Ltd*	18	10	55
6	Chris Ejik Int'l Agencies Ltd*	18	12	66
7	Njonas Engineering Nig Ltd*	22	8	36
8	Metrohamon Engineering Ltd*	20	9	45
9	Veetek Nigeria Ltd**	8	5	62
10	Diyokes Consultants Ltd**	15	6	40
	Total	201	92	46

Source: Researchers computations from field study, 2025.

Table 3 above presents the questionnaire return rate from the different organizations involved in this study. The table shows that the return rate was not quite impressive with a total of 92 questionnaires out of 201 originally administered. This represents a slightly below average performance of 46% return rate. Chris Ejik Int'l Agencies, Veetek Nigeria, and Bureau of public procurements were the top performers while Akiota Works and Njonas Engineering were the worst performers. Thus our final sample size for this study is 92 individuals.

Analysis of Responses to Introductory Questions

In this section, we analyze the responses to the introductory questions of the study.

Fig. 1 Gender Distribution

Figure 1 presents the analysis of the gender composition of the study. It shows that 43% of the sample population are males while 57% of them are females.

Fig 2 Marital Status

The figure above shows that 59% of them are married, 34.5% of them are single, 0% are divorced while 6.5% of them are separated.

Fig. 3 Length of Service

27% have worked with the firm for a maximum of three years, 33% have worked with their organizations for a maximum of 6 years while 40% of them have worked for seven years and above.

On educational qualification presented in figure 4.4 below, 5.4% of the sample population hold an Ordinary Level certificate in education which is an equivalent of a secondary school education in Nigeria. Another 5.4% possess a master’s degree or some higher qualification but 40.2% possess a National Diploma while 49% possess a first degree from a university or its equivalent.

Fig. 4 Level of Education of the respondents

Fig. 5 Job Status

Of the 92 individuals included in the survey, 2 persons representing 2.2% of the sample size are in the senior management category, 8 persons representing 8.7% of the sample are in the mid-management cadre, 28 respondents representing 30.4% of them are senior staff members while 54 employees representing 58.7% of the sample size are in the junior staff category.

Fig. 6 Age Distribution of the Sample

The age bracket of 36-40 holds the modal class of the sample with 26 individuals while the group with the least membership is the group of 51+ with only 4 members.

Analysis of Research Questions

The tabulated analysis of the research questions can be found in Appendix 1

Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: Cash-flow forecasting has no significant relationship with final project outcome.

Table 4: Summary of Responses for Ho₁

PROPOSITIONS CAPTURING HO1	AGREE	DISAGREE	TOTAL
Proposition 1	48	44	92
Proposition 2	40	52	92
Proposition 3	65	27	92
Proposition 4	39	53	92
Proposition 5	32	60	92
Proposition 6	50	42	92
Proposition 7	53	39	92
Total	327	317	644

Source: Researchers computations from field study, 2025.

Table 5 Calculation of cell values for Ho₁

S/N	Calculations for Agreement		Calculations for Disagreement	
1	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
2	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
3	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
4	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
5	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
6	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45
7	$\frac{327 \times 92}{644}$	47	$\frac{317 \times 92}{644}$	45

Source: Researchers computations from field study, 2025.

Table 6 Table of Contingence for Ho₁

Observed F(O)	Expected F(E)	O-E	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² / E
1	48	1	1	0
2	40	-7	49	1.0
3	65	18	324	6.9
4	39	-8	64	1.4
5	32	-15	225	4.8
6	50	3	9	0.2
7	53	6	36	0.8
8	44	-1	1	0
9	52	7	49	1.2
10	27	18	324	7.2
11	53	8	64	1.4
12	60	15	225	5
13	42	-3	9	0.2
14	39	-6	36	0.8
X² Calculated				30.9

Source: Researchers computations from field study, 2025.

Decision Rule:

If X^2 calculated at 5% critical level is $>X^2$ tabulated, reject H_0 (that is, accept H_1) and conclude that the variable in question has significant relationship with the phenomenon studied. Accept H_0 and conclude otherwise if the reverse is the case.

Note: For this test, the 5% critical level under normal distribution is determined at the point of intersection of the Row by Column Matrix after adjustment for the degrees of freedom and then number of propositions. i.e,

No of Rows = 14, No of columns = 5. Degrees of freedom is 1 on both row and column and number of propositions is 7. Therefore the 5% critical value is:

$$(14-1) \times (5-1) = 13 \times 4 = 52/7 = 7.4$$

Checking the value of 52 under 0.05 at the students “t” statistic table gives 47.83 Therefore our benchmark control value for this test is 7.4 Empirical values of X^2 above 7.4 imply rejection of the null hypothesis while empirical X^2 values below it imply acceptance of the null hypothesis.

Conclusion

Since our empirical X^2 calculated at 5% critical level is 30.9 which is $>X^2$ tabulated (7.4), we therefore Reject H_0 (that is, Accept H_1) and conclude that Cash-flow forecasting has significant relationship with final project outcome.

Test of Hypothesis 2

Advance payments have no significant effects on project Mile Stone Achievements

Table 7: Summary of Responses for Ho2

	PROPOSITIONS CAPTURING HO1	AGREE	DISAGREE	TOTAL
	Proposition 8	42	50	92
	Proposition 9	34	58	92
	Proposition 10	40	52	92
	Proposition 11	40	52	92
	Proposition 12	42	50	92
	Proposition 13	52	40	92
	Proposition 14	30	62	92
	Total	280	364	644

Source: Researchers computations from field study, 2025.

Table 8 Calculation of cell values for Ho₁

S/N	Calculations for Agreement		Calculations for Disagreement	
1	280 x 92 644	40	364 x 92 644	52
2	280 x 92 644	40	364 x 92 644	52
3	280 x 92 644	40	364 x 92 644	52
4	280 x 92 644	40	364 x 92 644	52
5	280 x 92 644	40	364 x 92 644	52
6	280 x 92 644	40	364 x 92 644	52
7	280 x 92 644	40	364 x 92 644	52

Source: Researchers computations from field study, 2025.

Table 9 of Contingence for Ho₁

Observed (O)	Expected (E)	(O-E)	(O-E) ²	(O-E) ² / E	
1	42	40	2	4	0.1
2	34	40	-6	36	0.9
3	40	40	0	0	0
4	40	40	0	0	0
5	42	40	2	4	0.1
6	52	40	12	144	3.6
7	30	40	-10	100	2.5
8	50	52	-2	4	0
9	58	52	6	36	0.7
10	52	52	0	0	0
11	52	52	0	0	0
12	50	52	-2	4	0
13	40	52	-12	144	2.8
14	62	52	10	100	1.9
X² Calculated				12.6	

Source: Researchers computations from field study, 2025.

Decision Rule:

Our decision rule remains as stated in hypothesis 1 above.

Conclusion

Since our empirical X² calculated at 5% critical level is 12.6 which is > X² tabulated (7.4), we Reject Ho (that is, accept H₁) and conclude that advance payments have significant effects on project Mile Stone Achievements

Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary of Findings

In this study, the effectiveness of cash-flow management on successful project delivery was studied. The study was motivated by the growing rate at which projects outcomes vary from their expected value in Nigeria and the increasing rate at which projects totally fail or get abandoned irrespective of the resources committed to them. The empirical study showed that if proper financing options are adhered to by the project issuer, the contractor is likely to live up to the expectations and the project is likely to turn out good, all other things being equal. The survey which

involved 92 respondents drawn from different stake holder organizations in the project management industry and adopted the simple non-parametric X^2 analytical tool made the following findings:

- i. The relationship between Cash-flow forecasting and final project outcome had a value of 30.9 which is greater than the theoretical control value at the 5% critical level which is 7.4. This led to the rejection of the Null Hypothesis that Cash-flow forecasting has no significant relationship with final project outcome.
- ii. The second finding was that advance payments which, of course, help to sustain a steady positive cash-flow have significant effects on project Mile Stone Achievements. This has a positive knock-on effect of the final project outcome. The empirical value of the test for this turned up a value of 12.6 which is also greater than the control value at the 5% critical level which is 7.4 thus again leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis for this test.

Conclusion

Based on the above findings, this study concludes that cash-flow management has significant impact on successful project delivery. Put differently, the findings reveal that if the cash flow of the project is right, several other factors that help ensure that the project outcome is good are always right and the chances that the project comes out good is usually very high. This is easy to understand since the cash flow gives a clear signal as to the financial profitability and viability of the project.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the following recommendations are made:

- i. Job issuers should make a reliable cash-flow analysis and forecasting for the job ahead of commencement. This should be a vital part of the feasibility study conducted prior to the commencement of the project. This has the advantage of helping the owner know the revenue expectations from the project, the periodic inflows and the costs and help him to appropriate his resources accordingly.
- ii. There is need for the job issuer to also consider progress payments. This is a sort of paying the contractor ahead of each planned tranche of the project and empowers the contractor to move on with the job without incurring any unnecessary delays. It also helps to beat impending inflationary pressures that would otherwise cause the budget price of the project to surge upwards which can also lead to either total abandonment of the project or the compromise of project quality and standard in a bid to manage cost.
- iii. Job issuers are also advised to consider milestones payments model for their projects. This will also produce a similar effect as that of progress payments but should be applied on the condition that the contractor must be financially buoyant to shoulder the responsibilities of funding each tranche of the job sufficiently to completion before he is paid. If the contractor does not have the financial backing to do this, the job issuer should apply the progress. However, when milestones payment are properly applied, they ensure quick quality completion of the job.
- iv. Stakeholders to the project; the job issuer, contractor and the consultant should regularly meet and liaise over job funding moderlities and progress so that any errors along the line are discovered, discussed and corrected early in the job.

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